

NFDI4Chem, Chemistry Consortium in the NFDI

Deliverable D4.4.1

50 Experimental processes and data publications using NFDI4Chem infrastructure and beyond

TA4 – Metadata, Data Standards and Publication Standards

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Content

Executive Summary	3
Project objectives	3
Detailed report on the deliverable	4
Background	4
Description of Work	4
Manual Acquisition of Data Contributors and Datasets	4
Finding published datasets	6
NFDI4Chem Search Service	6
Google dataset search	7
DataCite PID Graph	8
Use of datasets	11
Hygrophorus and their deoxy-Hygrophorones	11
Pulegone, Linderazuelene and Carminic Acid	14
Publish data from RADAR dataset in Chemotion Repository and nmrXiv	16
Chemotion Repository	17
nmrXiv	18
Lessons learned	19
Risks and Mitigation	19
Next steps	19

Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of the activities in Measure 4.4: Lead-by-Example: Creation and deposition of substantial standards compliant datasets.

The aim of these activities were to

1. collect representative, real as well as substantially complex datasets from diverse chemistry subdisciplines,
2. verify the findability of datasets, and
3. use these datasets to test NFDI4Chem services under development.

The Lead-by-Example data also serves to inspire researchers on what is already possible today and documents the process to FAIRify research data publication.

This goal was achieved by

1. actively seeking and supporting data deposition by consortium partners, external collaborators and early adopters from the chemistry community, and
2. by using several data search engines to find datasets by project partners, and
3. resubmit datasets to specific services of NFDI4Chem to provide detailed feedback for improvements to the developers.

Project objectives

This deliverable has contributed particularly to the **Objective 4.1** of TA4 to provide a set of coherent and interoperable data standards.

Moreover, this deliverable has contributed and *will continue to contribute* to the following key objectives in NFDI4Chem¹:

Key Objective 1 to develop and establish a virtual environment of federated repositories for storing, disclosing, searching and reusing research data and to build one or multiple domain-specific research data repositories for the national research community, and link them to international repositories.

Key Objective 4 to engage with the chemistry community in Germany to create awareness for, and foster the adoption of FAIR data management and to offer information materials for researchers.

Key Objective 6 to provide a framework of policies and guidelines for FAIR research data management.

¹ C. Steinbeck, O. Koepler, F. Bach, S. Herres-Pawlis, N. Jung, J. C. Liermann, S. Neumann, M. Razum, C. Baldauf, F. Biedermann, T. W. Bocklitz, F. Boehm, F. Broda, P. Czodrowski, T. Engel, M. G. Hicks, S. M. Kast, C. Kettner, W. Koch, G. Lanza, A. Link, R. A. Mata, W. E. Nagel, A. Porzel, N. Schlörer, T. Schulze, H.-G. Weinig, W. Wenzel, L. A. Wessjohann, S. Wulle, NFDI4Chem - Towards a National Research Data Infrastructure for Chemistry in Germany, *RIO* **2020**, 6, e55852, DOI: [10.3897/rio.6.e55852](https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.6.e55852).

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background

This deliverable is part of the activities in Measure 4.4 Lead-by-Example: Creation and deposition of a substantial set of standards compliant datasets.

The development of standards for metadata, minimum information, analytical data formats and publication standards encompasses guidelines and specifications as well as reference implementations and also example instances of data encoded in a gradually evolving standard-compliant manner. To publish supplemental dataset(s) beyond the common practice to submit supplementary information in PDF format, we take leadership in chemistry research data management by the provision of best-practice example datasets. The documentation and evaluation of the process to FAIRify chemistry research data unravels practical issues and enables suggestions for improvement to be fed back to other projects within NFDI4Chem.

The main task of this measure was the identification and collection of real chemistry datasets. Manual processing of data was required, as seamless workflows to treat chemistry research data as envisioned by NFDI4Chem did not exist yet for all types of chemistry data. Until the standards, systems and processes are finalised, the Lead-by-Example datasets were and *will be* used for testing, validation, stress-tests, but also for educational purposes and community outreach.

Description of Work

Manual Acquisition of Data Contributors and Datasets

For the structured acquisition of datasets, we created a [web form](#) (Figure 1) to collect relevant information about the datasets from all contributors. We also allowed contributors to email us via lead-by-example.nfdi4chem@ipb-halle.de, in case this was preferred by the contributors.

The form address as well as the email address was advertised during consortium meetings (1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and finally 3.0), on Twitter², the NFDI4Chem website³, our quarterly Newsletter⁴ and personal contact to external researchers in institutions which take part in NFDI4Chem and beyond. The data pledge was also featured in the NFDI4Chem Stammtisch Talk on 25th March, 2022: *Lead-by-example: Pragmatic RDM in Chemistry by Dr. Steffen Neumann*⁵, which is available on YouTube⁶.

² Twitter: [NFDI4Chem/.../1354029035525976064](https://twitter.com/NFDI4Chem/.../1354029035525976064) and [sneumannoffice/.../1357340858190766081](https://twitter.com/sneumannoffice/.../1357340858190766081)

³ NFDI4Chem News Post [11/2020](#), [02/2022](#) and [12/2022](#).

⁴ Newsletter: [6th NFDI4Chem Newsletter](#) and [9th NFDI4Chem newsletter](#).

⁵ Pragmatic RDM in Chemistry (Dr. Steffen Neumann), Slides: <https://ogy.de/npik>.

⁶ Pragmatic RDM in Chemistry (Dr. Steffen Neumann), Recording: https://youtu.be/5z_QN-xBd-o.

Together with the contributors we established whether support by Lead-by-Example members was required, either in the form of light-weight consulting, or more involved data stewardship support.

While internal contributors from within NFDI4Chem who replied via the web form did not require any data stewardship support and members of Lead-by-Example only rarely encountered the need for consulting, external contributors required us to help in the preparation of their datasets to get them ready to be published. This also included suggestions for suitable chemistry-friendly research data repositories and help for questions on licensing.

Lead-by-Example: Pledge Your Dataset!

We aim to provide a large body of real datasets prepared in a standard-compliant manner. Please suggest your datasets in the form below, add a DOI to a publication for which you want to also publish the dataset or add details to an currently unpublished dataset. We will approach you for the details and to see where we can help with the preparation. A suitable repository will also be suggested.

In case you would like to contribute with an unpublished manuscript, you may send the manuscript (or instructions as to how to securely access the manuscript) to lead-by-example.nfdi4chem@jpb-halle.de. Having a ready to publish dataset before your manuscript gets published, will enable you to add the DOI of your dataset to the data availability statement of the publication. This will increase the findability of your dataset.

We guarantee to keep unpublished work as highly confidential, with the number of people given access being limited and carefully regulated.

See also our post at [nfdi4chem.de](https://www.nfdi4chem.de)

<https://www.nfdi4chem.de/index.php/2022/02/02/data-pledge-lets-lead-by-example-2/>

Thanks in advance!

Figure 1: [Web Form](#) to collect dataset information.

At a later stage, several groups and individuals were contacted to acquire datasets with specific so far missing characteristics, such as particular data types and/or chemistry disciplines which were not covered.

The first external contribution which required our data stewardship service was a study on fungi of the genus *Hygrophorus* and their deoxy-hygrophorones⁷. Some datasets requiring data stewardship were even pledged on behalf of the authors. Namely, a series⁸ of 30 natural products and their isolation and characterisation was submitted via our survey form.

At the point of writing this deliverable, we collected 20 pairs of scientific publications and their corresponding dataset(s) plus one dataset from the field of medicinal chemistry still under curation.

⁷ T. Ditfe, E. Bette, H. N. Sultani, A. Otto, L. A. Wessjohann, N. Arnold, B. Westermann, Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Highly Potent Fungicidal Deoxy-Hygrophorones, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2021**, 3827. DOI: [10.1002/ejoc.202100729](https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.202100729).

⁸ D. Sicker, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, [Naturstoffe isolieren und charakterisieren](#), *ChiuZ* **2019**, 53, 74. DOI: [10.1002/ciuz.201970202](https://doi.org/10.1002/ciuz.201970202).

The collection of 50 pairs of scientific articles with their dataset(s), could have been filled up easily with already published datasets by internal contributors of NFDI4Chem. They are not of a diverse nature, so they were not explicitly listed.

Finding published datasets

In parallel to the collection of datasets through the Lead-by-Example web form, some consortium members have implemented data publication into their regular research publication workflows. Instead of asking to manually submit these datasets to the submission form to fill up the list to 50 datasets (see above), we went a step further. We show how datasets of one selected researcher, Prof. Dr. Sonja Herres-Pawlis, with already three contributions to Lead-by-Example and further datasets (not part of Lead-by-Example) can actually be found through several data search engines.

NFDI4Chem Search Service

The NFDI4Chem Search Service (search.nfdi4chem.de) is a metasearch engine for NFDI4Chem related repositories and databases. The service is currently under development. It is possible to search for datasets in the [MassBank EU](#) reference spectral database, in the [Chemotion Repository](#), [RADAR](#) and [RADAR4Chem](#). Other repositories such as CSD from CCDC are not yet supported.

The screenshot displays the NFDI4Chem search interface. At the top, there are navigation links for 'Repositories', 'Datasets', 'About', and 'Help'. The main content area shows a search bar with the query 'Herres-Pawlis' and a search button. Below the search bar, it indicates '355 datasets found for "Herres-Pawlis"' and an 'Order by: Relevance' dropdown menu. The search results are listed in a table-like format, with each entry including a title, a brief description, and a link to view the dataset in HTML format. The first result is 'methyl 2-[bis(dimethylamino)methyleneamino]-5-(dimethylamino)benzoate', followed by '1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR) (methyl 2-[bis(dimethylamino)methyleneamino]-5-(dimethylamino)benzoate)', and 'mass spectrometry (MS) (methyl 2-[bis(dimethylamino)methyleneamino]-5-(dimethylamino)benzoate)'. On the left side, there is a sidebar with 'Repository' and 'Tags' filters. The 'Repository' filter shows 'Chemotion - Reposit...' with 351 results and 'Radar4Chem' with 4 results. The 'Tags' filter shows various categories like 'chemistry' (323), '13c-nmr' (60), '1h-nmr' (60), 'ir' (41), 'mass-spectrometry' (34), 'chemical-reaction-s...' (32), 'dataset' (4), 'engineering' (2), 'density-functional...' (1), and 'dft-optimised-coord...' (1). There is also a 'Show More Tags' button and a 'Formats' dropdown menu.

Figure 2: Searching for datasets by 'herres-pawlis' reports four datasets in RADAR4Chem, and 351 in the Chemotion Repository. Source: search.nfdi4chem.de/.../?q=Herres-Pawlis (checked 21st December, 2022). The search service is able to extract additional tags and metadata from the metadata served by the individual resources.

The service will query the full text of the datasets, but an advanced search allows the user to select the queried fields. Search results can be filtered by various metadata. In contrast

to the PID Graph (see below) the user can only search for data provided by the repositories. Searching for a specific person via the ORCID iD is (at time of this writing) not available.

Google dataset search

Google is indexing structured data in their search services. To make datasets discoverable by Google, the resource provider, e.g. a repository or database, has to provide metadata about the dataset in their public web pages. At the moment the service can read three formats of metadata information⁹: schema.org Dataset¹⁰ markup (recommended), W3C's Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) format¹¹ and W3C CSV on the Web (CSVW)¹². Beside the Dataset type, Google also reads schema.org types DataCatalog and DataDownload. The search can query all fields of provided metadata information, and the results from all sources are presented in an uniform way. For further information, the user can follow the links to the data and metadata.

Figure 3: Searching for datasets by 'herres-pawlis' in Google dataset search. Source: datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?query=herres-pawlis (checked 10st February, 2023).

A search for 'herres-pawlis' (Figure 3) will result in 42 datasets, most of them found in The Cambridge Structural Database DataCite, and one each from Zenodo and figshare, both related to text publications. The known-to-exist datasets in Chemotion Repository or

⁹ Dataset structured data (Dataset, DataCatalog, DataDownload), URL: <https://developers.google.com/search/docs/appearance/structured-data/dataset>.

¹⁰ Schema.org Datasets, A Schema.org Type, URL: <https://schema.org/Dataset>.

¹¹ Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 2, URL: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>.

¹² CSV on the Web Working Group, https://www.w3.org/2013/csvw/wiki/Main_Page (last checked 21st December 2022).

RADAR4Chem were not found, which was forwarded to the repository team as an enhancement request. Moreover, google dataset search does not currently support search via ORCID iDs.

DataCite PID Graph

Datasets are connected to all kinds of accompanying information, e.g. authors and contributors, publications, software or repositories, which can also be identified by persistent identifiers (PIDs). These are associated with a set of metadata and links to other identifiable digital objects. This network of PIDs representing resources and metadata can be described by a graph of nodes identified by the PIDs and edges to model the connections between these nodes. This model was introduced in 2019 as the PID graph¹³.

The DataCite PID graph is one of the first implementations of the model. It can be used to find datasets by querying not only PIDs but also by providing hints for a metadata search on referencing PIDs. Thus, it is possible to search for datasets associated with an ORCID iD, which is a PID representing a researcher, or to find datasets which have contributions from an institution by providing the name of the institution.

Query

```
{
  person(id: "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4354-4353") {
    id
    name
    givenName
    familyName
    citationCount
    works(resourceType: "Dataset") {
      totalCount
      published {
        title
        count
      }
      nodes {
        id
        type
        titles {
          title
        }
        rights {
          rights
        }
        citationCount
      }
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 4: GraphQL query (checked 21st December, 2022) for searching for subsets of the metadata of datasets by ORCID iD 0000-0002-4354-4353 and resource type (“Dataset”). The GraphQL API can be tested under <https://api.datacite.org/graphql>.

¹³ Introducing the PID Graph, DataCite Blog, <https://doi.org/10.5438/jwvf-8a66> (last checked 21st December 2022).

The DataCite PID graph can be queried by the JSON REST API or for more complex queries by the DataCite GraphQL API. While the first allows the discovery of relations between nodes via an intermediary connection, the latter allows one to query and filter the entire network of associated PIDs by constructing complex queries with the GraphQL query language.

Accessing data in the PID Graph is also possible via DataCite Commons. Whereas the construction of queries for the APIs requires some knowledge of the query syntax, DataCite Commons provides a simpler frontend for searching the PID Graph, allowing queries by less experienced users.

Result

```
{
  "data": {
    "person": {
      "id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4354-4353",
      "name": "Sonja Herres-Pawlis",
      "givenName": "Sonja",
      "familyName": "Herres-Pawlis",
      "citationCount": 124,
      "works": {
        "totalCount": 133,
        "published": [
          {
            "title": "2022",
            "count": 133
          }
        ]
      },
      "nodes": [
        {
          "id":
"https://doi.org/10.14272/acofzhhylnxzfzfv-uhfffaoyisa-n/chmo0000593",
          "type": "Dataset",
          "titles": [
            {
              "title": "1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR) ()"
            },
            {
              "title":
"InChI=1S/C20H28N4/c1-23(2)20(24(3)4)22-18-12-8-11-16-13-14-17(21-19(16)18)15-9-6-5-7-10-15/h8,11-15H,5-7,9-10H2,1-4H3"
            }
          ]
        },
        {
          "rights": [
            {
              "rights": "Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International"
            }
          ]
        },
        {
          "citationCount": 0
        }
      ],
      [...]
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 5: GraphQL result (checked 21st December, 2022) for searching for some metadata of datasets by ORCID iD 0000-0002-4354-4353 and resource type (“Dataset”). The GraphQL API can be tested under <https://api.datacite.org/graphql>.

As the PID graph search will query linked PIDs, a simple search for the name of a person does not yield reliable search results. To get the desired result, the user has to use some persistent identifier for the person, which usually is the ORCID iD¹⁴ for researchers. Figures 4 and 5 show the query and result for a DataCite GraphQL search for datasets associated with Sonja Herres-Pawlis (ORCID iD: 0000-0002-4354-4353). The result contains only 133 (21st December 2022) datasets (Figure 4 and 5) whereas the search in DataCite Commons yields 181 results (Figure 6), as the GraphQL API omits all datasets without an explicit licence. By searching for “Sonja Herres-Pawlis” in the classic DataCite search, the user gets 738 datasets¹⁵ (21st December 2022), but these contain all datasets with “Sonja” AND “Herres-Pawlis” (without abbreviation), and might be not specific enough.

Figure 6: Result page of DataCite Commons with the ORCID iD 0000-0002-4354-4353 (Sonja Herres-Pawlis) as query (checked 21st December, 2022).

commons.datacite.org/orcid.org/0000-0002-4354-4353?orcid=0000-0002-4354-4353&resource-type=dataset

The search results show that the various search engines for datasets bring up different results due to the distinct sources and harvesting approaches they use for their metadata search. It also demonstrates that the name is not an unambiguous identifier for the creator of a dataset. In our examples, we used a remarkable last name triggering no false positive results. The inclusion of the first name in the query results in a reduced quantity of hits because of the varying handling of first names in metadata, e.g. sometimes first names are abbreviated or second names are present or not. The best way to find datasets of a specific creator is to use the ORCID iD since it is unique for any researcher. However, this has the disadvantage that older datasets which predate the use of the ORCID iD may be missing from the results. To improve findability (and thus FAIRness) of published datasets (and of course other publications) the ORCID iDs should be used where possible.

¹⁴ ORCID, URL: <https://orcid.org/>.

¹⁵ DataCite Search, <https://search.datacite.org/?query=sonja+herres-pawlis&resource-type-id=dataset> (last checked 21st December 2022).

Use of datasets

The Lead-by-Example datasets were re-used in several of NFDI4Chem resources. Initially, we created an article in the [NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base](#) (Figure 6 and 7), also to advertise our work to motivate researchers to submit their work. All current and also upcoming contributions were and *will* be highlighted in the [Lead-by-Example section in NFDI4Chem's Knowledge Base](#), providing an introduction and a dynamic representation using a React component (Figure 7) to filter by repositories, chemistry subdisciplines and journals, for which a low-entry-level workflow¹⁶ was established for adding data. Furthermore, the datasets in the Lead-by-Example section of our Knowledge Base are also interlinked to other sections within the domains category, e.g. for a [synthetic organic/inorganic chemist](#).

Figure 6: Screenshot of NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base, <https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/>.

Hygrophorus and their *deoxy*-Hygrophorones

The first external contribution which required our data stewardship service was a study on fungi of the genus *Hygrophorus* and their *deoxy*-hygrophorones¹⁷. The corresponding dataset, now published aided by the Lead-by-Example stewardship service according to the

¹⁶ The workflow includes a google apps script converting a (bidimensional) [google sheet](#) (low-entry) to a (multidimensional) JSON file, which is then fed via [GitHub](#) to the React component generating the [tables](#).

¹⁷ T. Ditte, E. Bette, H. N. Sultani, A. Otto, L. A. Wessjohann, N. Arnold, B. Westermann, Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Highly Potent Fungicidal *Deoxy*-Hygrophorones, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2021**, 3827, DOI: [10.1002/ejoc.202100729](https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.202100729).

wishes of the researchers in the generic research data repository RADAR¹⁸, contains original raw data in proprietary formats obtained from samples of pure compounds. All analytical data files were converted under our stewardship to interoperable open formats such as JCAMP-DX¹⁹ for NMR data and mzML²⁰ for MS data (see Figure 8) to enhance the interoperability following the FAIR data principles.

Figure 7: Screenshot of Lead-by-Example Datasets in NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base, <https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/docs/datasets>.

Besides the RADAR metadata²¹, efforts of data stewardship focused on the description of the analytical data itself, especially by linking data to chemical structures. All structures are also available in a machine-readable data format (CTfiles), for which the summary was forged into an article on [CTfile formats](#) for the NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base. Furthermore, a supplementary table was designed to link

1. analytical data files named following lab notebook entries with

¹⁸ T. Ditfe, E. Bette, H. N. Sultani, A. Otto, L. A. Wessjohann, N. Arnold, B. Westermann, T. G. Fischer (data curator), Supplementary data for “Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Highly Potent Fungicidal Deoxy-Hygrophorones”, *RADAR* **2021**, DOI: [10.22000/451](https://doi.org/10.22000/451).

¹⁹ Linking of data in JCAMP-DX format to chemical structures could be obtained with JCAMP-CS, though, has not found adoption since its [specification](#) in 1991.

²⁰ Linking of data in mzML format to chemical structures via InChI or SMILES is not specified in mzML 1.1.0 [specification](#) for reasons of having the minimal required set of tags in mzML. Not all (meta)data in vendor files is necessarily retained, while converting to mzML, hence, original raw data should be published along the data in open formats.

²¹ RADAR metadata link to the corresponding scientific publication via its DOI as a related identifier with relation type IsSupplement to, following DataCite’s metadata schema 4.4 [documentation](#) and CrossRefs documentation on [relations](#).

2. numbering of corresponding chemical structures in the associated scientific publication,
3. their structural representation as SMILES structure codes and
4. their unambiguous identification with InChI (and InChIKey) identifiers.

What does the dataset contain?

Figure 8: Content (v1.0) of dataset of hygrophorones⁶ published in the generic research data repository RADAR.

These experiences were combined into an [article on machine-readable chemical structures and supplementary tables](#) to enhance machine-readability of structures in datasets published in generic repositories such as RADAR for the NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base (Figure 9). This includes a tutorial on how to retrieve this data and additional template table files.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Local chemical stru	local chemical sample	IUPAC_name	SMILES	InChI	InChIKey
2	CHEMINF:	CHEMINF:	CHEMINF:000107	CHEMINF:000020	CHEMINF:000038	CHEMINF:0
3	http://semanticscie	http://semanticscienc	http://semanticscier	http://semanticscie	http://semanticsci	http://sem
4	1	NF-0007	1-phenylethanone	<chem>CC(C1=CC=CC=C1)=</chem>	InChI=1S/C8H8O/c	KWOLFJPF
5	2	NF-0789	(2S)-2-aminopropan	<chem>N[C@@H](C)C(O)=</chem>	InChI=1S/C3H7NO	QNAYBMK
6	3	NF-1245	(R)-[(2S,4S,5R)-5-eth	<chem>[H][C@@]1([C@@</chem>	InChI=1S/C20H24N	LOUPRKON

Figure 9: Supplementary table to enhance machine-readability of dataset published in generic research data repositories such as RADAR, see *Knowledge Base* [article](#).

This table is also enhanced and linked with terms from ontologies. While the Chemical Information Ontology (CHEMINF) and the SemanticScience Integrated Ontology (SIO) provide links for most of the terms used in this table, ontological definitions on lab notebook entries or local chemical sample symbols²² and numbering of chemical structures in

²² Following the Information Artifact Ontology (IAO) and identifier is an information content entity that requires a dubbing process, such as a resolver for PIDs. Symbols apply in a more general sense as a mark to represent another entity.

scientific publications or local chemical structure symbol were missing. They have been requested²³ to be added to CHEMINF.

The compilation of tables with machine-readability content of the research data can be quite tedious on a case by case basis. Therefore, only the aforementioned four aspects are recommended, while further information is optional. Furthermore, only data publications in generic research data repositories such as RADAR will profit from such a table, while structured field-specific repositories such as Chemotion Repository together with Chemotion ELN already capture such information by design.

For generic repositories, which usually do not provide this information, this table could also be superseded by (open, interoperable) data formats covering metadata including chemical structure notations and identifiers. Alternatively, metadata might wrap analytical data in open formats. Hence, the table described above might only be a vehicle to enhance machine-readability until these features are implemented for analytical data formats and these formats are implemented in research software to generate these files.

As the manuscript to be sent to a scientific journal was still under preparation, Lead-by-Example also assisted in referencing the dataset in the back matter of the manuscript in a Data Availability Statement (DAS) via its DOI. There were no general recommendations in the author guidelines of the respective journal on how to reference corresponding datasets at this time. The author guidelines also did not provide any templates for DAS. Discussions on DAS with the authors and the editor of the journal were then continued in Measure 4.5 on Publication Standards and the Editors4Chem Workshop Nov/2021 and were again fed back to another [article on Data availability statements](#) in the NFDI4Chem *Knowledge Base*, also providing FAIR data principle compliant templates.

Pulegone, Linderazuelene and Carminic Acid

The series²⁴ of 30 natural products and their isolation and characterisation required intense data stewardship to include three of these datasets in Lead-by-Example. This indeed turned out to be rather complex (*cf.* data archeology), labour intensive and time consuming. Nevertheless, the process of intense data stewardship together with the Hygrophorus and the consulting service for all other contributors forged a list on how to prepare datasets for publication, with a focus on generic research data repositories. This list was included in the NFDI4Chem *Knowledge Base* article on [Best Practices](#) within the section [Data Publication](#). This also provided valuable resources for already published and future articles in NFDI4Chem's *Knowledge Base* focusing on Data Publication.

The dataset²⁵ on the isolation of linderazuelene²⁶, a strikingly interesting small aromatic organic molecule with purple colour not following the photochemical dogma also called

²³ P. Strömert, T. G. Fischer, GitHub **2022**, URL: <https://github.com/.../semanticchemistry/issues/54>.

²⁴ D. Sicker, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, [Naturstoffe isolieren und charakterisieren](#), *ChiuZ* **2019**, 53, 74. DOI: [10.1002/ciuz.201970202](https://doi.org/10.1002/ciuz.201970202).

²⁵ N. Keltsch, V. Munzert, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), Dataset: Linderazuelene aus einer invasiven Pflanze, *RADAR4Chem* **2022**, DOI: [10.22000/786](https://doi.org/10.22000/786).

²⁶ N. Keltsch, V. Munzert, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, Linderazuelene aus einer invasiven Pflanze, *ChiuZ* **2019**, 53, 92-102. DOI: [10.1002/ciuz.201900868](https://doi.org/10.1002/ciuz.201900868).

Kasha's Rule²⁷, contains NMR, UV/VIS and IR data in vendor formats and as JCAMP-DX as well as MS data in vendor formats and as mzML (Figure 10). Moreover, the supplementary table is provided, but this information is now also provided in SDfiles of linderazulene and chamazulene, for which UV/VIS data is part of the dataset for reasons of comparability. Finally, a README file in Markdown and rendered as HTML to enhance human readability covers general information as well as provenance information on the location of sample collection, data generation as well as the instruments used. To overcome supplemental PDFs, this README should include all information provided in the supplemental PDF which is not published as/in analytical data files within a dataset.

What does the dataset contain?

Figure 10: Content (v2.0) of dataset of linderazulene published in the generic research data repository RADAR4Chem.

Other datasets^{28,29} of (*R*)-(+)-pulegone³⁰ and carminic acid³¹ were curated with a similar approach and structure and were also published in RADAR4Chem.

While preparing all four dataset for publication in RADAR and RADAR4Chem, we encountered some issues with the RADAR infrastructure. These issues include suggestions on changes to the embargo feature and possible copyright violations by authors with the metadata field “abstract”, which might require and have received an additional tooltip or documentation. Also RADAR4Chem branding issues, missing implementation of the research organisation registry (ROR) and concept DOIs, the ability to wrap several datasets corresponding to a scientific publication, tooltips on relation types to be used to link scientific publications with their corresponding datasets and an issue with the upload of

²⁷ V. Balzani, P. Ceroni, A. Juris, *Photochemistry and Photophysics: Concepts, Research, Applications*; Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, 2014.

²⁸ A. Prasse, V. Munzert, E. José, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), Dataset: Die Polei-Minze im Wandel der Zeiten, *RADAR4Chem* **2022**, DOI: [10.22000/785](https://doi.org/10.22000/785).

²⁹ F. Schulze, J. Titus, P. Mettke, S. Berger, H.-U. Siehl, K.-P. Zeller, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), Dataset: Karminsäure - Das Rot aus Cochenilleläusen, *RADAR4Chem* **2022**, DOI: [10.22000/795](https://doi.org/10.22000/795).

³⁰ A. Prasse, V. Munzert, E. José, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, Die Polei-Minze im Wandel der Zeiten, *ChiuZ* **2018**, 53, 28-38. DOI: [10.22000/785](https://doi.org/10.22000/785).

³¹ F. Schulze, J. Titus, P. Mettke, S. Berger, H.-U. Siehl, K.-P. Zeller, D. Sicker, Karminsäure - Das Rot aus Cochenilleläusen, *ChiuZ* **2013**, 47, 222-228. DOI: [10.1002/ciuz.201300634](https://doi.org/10.1002/ciuz.201300634).

data to non-empty datasets were reported to the RADAR developer team. All of these issues are going to be addressed within RADAR's next major release.

Publish data from RADAR dataset in Chemotion Repository and nmrXiv

We then went on and published selected data of these datasets to other field-specific research data repositories under development within NFDI4Chem, namely Chemotion Repository and nmrXiv, to test these repositories. Each repository comes with its own benefits and challenges. Being a generic research data repository, RADAR and RADAR4Chem have the intrinsic benefit of supporting all subdisciplines in chemistry, regardless of the type of data to be published. The upload is simple and fast. Though, research data management streamlines the process to collect a dataset ready to be uploaded. As manuscripts are prepared to be submitted to journals, datasets are prepared to be submitted to RADAR and RADAR4Chem. The submission system of a journal can be compared to the submission of a dataset including metadata in RADAR(4Chem).

On the other side, Chemotion Repository and nmrXiv are highly structured field-specific research data repositories, with a data model which allows for the collection of data in a highly structured way. Both repositories come with additional features such as spectral viewers to annotate spectral data. Hence, the data is machine-readable and may allow for data driven scientific approaches of reuse. While the quality of RADAR datasets highly depends on the research data management skills of the curating researcher to obtain an interoperable and reusable dataset, Chemotion Repository and nmrXiv pave the way to high quality research data publication via a multistep ingestion of data in a structured way – quality by design.

Issues encountered while adding datasets of the *deoxy-Hygrophorones*^{32,33}, linderazuelene^{34,35}, (*R*)-(+)-pulegone^{36,37} and carminic acid^{38,39} to Chemotion Repository and nmrXiv were reported via GitHub. This resembled in [10 issues](#) to Chemotion Repository and [28 issues](#) and [4 issues](#) brought to nmrXiv.

³² T. Ditfe, *Chemotion Repository* **2022**, DOI: [10.14272/collection/SQD_2022-10-04](https://doi.org/10.14272/collection/SQD_2022-10-04).

³³ T. Ditfe, E. Bette, H. Sultani, N. Arnold, L. Wessjohann, B. Westermann, *nmrXiv* **2022**, DOI: [10.57992/nmrxiv.p3](https://doi.org/10.57992/nmrxiv.p3).

³⁴ N. Keltsch, V. Munzert, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), Dataset: Linderazuelene, *Chemotion Repository* **2023**, DOI: [10.14272/LMVGRKPOXLBIFO-UHFFFAOYSA-N.1](https://doi.org/10.14272/LMVGRKPOXLBIFO-UHFFFAOYSA-N.1).

³⁵ N. Keltsch, V. Munzert, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), Dataset: Linderazuelene, *nmrXiv* **2022**, DOI: [10.57992/nmrxiv.p2](https://doi.org/10.57992/nmrxiv.p2).

³⁶ A. Prasse, V. Munzert, E. José, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), Dataset: Die Polei-Minze im Wandel der Zeiten, *Chemotion Repository* **2023**, DOI: [10.14272/NZGWDASTMWDZIW-MRVPVSSYSA-N.1](https://doi.org/10.14272/NZGWDASTMWDZIW-MRVPVSSYSA-N.1).

³⁷ A. Prasse, V. Munzert, E. José, K.-P. Zeller, H.-U. Siehl, S. Berger, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), NMR Dataset: Die Polei-Minze im Wandel der Zeiten, *nmrXiv* **2022**, DOI: [10.57992/nmrxiv.p16](https://doi.org/10.57992/nmrxiv.p16).

³⁸ F. Schulze, J. Titus, P. Mettke, S. Berger, H.-U. Siehl, K.-P. Zeller, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), NMR dataset: Karminsäure - Das Rot aus Cochenilleläusen, *Chemotion Repository* **2023**, DOI: [10.14272/DGQLVPJXVFOQEV-JNVSTXMASA-N.1](https://doi.org/10.14272/DGQLVPJXVFOQEV-JNVSTXMASA-N.1).

³⁹ F. Schulze, J. Titus, P. Mettke, S. Berger, H.-U. Siehl, K.-P. Zeller, D. Sicker, T. G. Fischer (data curator), NMR dataset: Karminsäure - Das Rot aus Cochenilleläusen, *nmrXiv* **2023**, DOI: [10.57992/nmrxiv.p17](https://doi.org/10.57992/nmrxiv.p17).

Chemotion Repository

In order to publish our chosen datasets in Chemotion, some adjustments to the data had to be made to keep up with its requirements. Chemotion(-Repository) is a repository which is sample and reaction centric, i.e. structured by samples and reactions and their corresponding (analytical) data. Unlike RADAR4Chem, the quality of the uploaded data is assessed and secured by both automated checks and manual review by scientists. While being usable as a standalone repository, Chemotion's full potential is best capitalised in the combination with a Chemotion ELN instance, as this enables the collection of high quality, structured data by design along the scientific workflows.

Using Chemotion Repository without collecting the data in Chemotion ELN proved to be labour and time intensive, as data from the RADAR dataset needed to be reorganised and manually uploaded again and annotated. Following the recommendations of Chemotion, for each reaction, all individual spectra were deposited as raw data, in an open interoperable format such as JCAMP-DX and for UV/VIS and IR data or mzML for MS data and as a PNG file⁴⁰, as well as including provenance information such as instruments.

The screenshot displays the Chemotion Repository web interface. On the left, a sidebar contains navigation options: 'Chemotion', 'Scheme-only reactions', 'My Published Elements', 'Pending Publications', 'Embargoed Publications', 'My Collections', 'All', 'ELN Gate', and 'My Data'. The main area shows a list of samples with columns for 'From', 'To', and 'Sample'. The selected sample, 'TIFI-2 Linderazulene', is highlighted in blue. Its details are shown on the right, including the chemical structure, molecular formula (C₁₅H₁₄O), name (1,5,8-trimethylazuleno[6,5-b]furan), and exact mass (210.104465 g/mol). Below the structure, there are tabs for 'Properties', 'Analyses', 'QC & curation', 'References', and 'Results'. The 'Analyses' tab is active, showing '1H NMR' and '13C NMR' data with 'Add to Report' buttons.

Figure 12: Screenshot from selected samples in Chemotion Repository.

Since each sample and reaction is published as a dataset on its own, each receives its own reaction DOI. However, all samples or reactions from each RADAR dataset or collection can now also be wrapped in one collection with one collection DOI, corresponding to one study.

⁴⁰ As further versions of Chemotion were released during consecutive submissions, the process of adding analytical data was improved to better recognize the raw data and create JCAMP-DX files and PNG pictures.

nmrXiv

The nmrXiv repository combines the simple data upload of RADAR4Chem with a more streamlined data structure, focussing on the analytical data created from NMR experiments with additional (meta)data such as chemical structures. The data model of nmrXiv is compatible with the ISA model. Each study has its own spectra datasets. All studies are then combined into an project⁴¹. This may also reflect a publication and its corresponding dataset. The combination of nmrXiv and NMRium⁴² not only allows for the recognition of various file formats, but also for the processing and annotation of the uploaded spectra.

The figure consists of two screenshots of the nmrXiv web application. The top screenshot shows the 'IPB HALLE DASHBOARD' for a user named 'TG TO'. The 'Projects' section displays a draft project titled 'Linderazulen aus einer invasiven Pflanze. Delphi und sein violettes Wunder.' by Steffen Neumann. The project description includes 'NMR dataset of Linderazuelene isolated from Smyrnium perfoliatum, collected close to the Monument to the Battle of Nations...' and is tagged with 'natural products', 'analytical chemistry', 'organic chemistry', and 'natural product chemistry'. The bottom screenshot shows a detailed view of a 13C NMR spectrum. The x-axis represents chemical shift in ppm, ranging from 220 to 0. A single sharp peak is visible at approximately 130 ppm. The interface includes a sidebar with various analysis tools and a right-hand panel with tabs for 'Spectra', 'Information', 'Peaks', 'Filters', 'Integrals', 'Ranges', and 'Chemical structures'.

Figure 12: Screenshots from nmrXiv.

⁴¹ People from Lead-by-Example had intense discussions with nmrXiv developers on the terminology used in nmrXiv. The ISA model provided the triplet investigation, study, assay. To move on to a chemistry-friendly terminology, the triplet investigation, sample, spectrum was suggested by Lead-by-Example, while nmrXiv developers decided for project, study, spectrum. Debate is ongoing.

⁴² NMRium, URL: <https://www.nmrium.org/>.

Lessons learned

During the described activities, it became abundantly clear that retrospective data collection and data curation are inherently difficult because scientists and data are not available anymore, instruments and software might have been sunset, or data was stored on some disks somewhere. More recent datasets and those under investigation were easier to collect. This documents the process of evolving FAIRness of chemistry research data. All of these prove again why research data management and data documentation from cradle-to-repository i.e. during the whole scientific process along workflows is required, and that activities in NFDI4Chem are timely.

Risks and Mitigation

Risk R4.2 '*Unwillingness to share data required to Lead-by-Example*' from the NFDI4Chem proposal did not occur, but it was a challenge to actually collect data from authors willing to share (*cf.* data archaeology). However, we would have loved to receive more contributions from outside NFDI4Chem and also from institutions not taking part in NFDI4Chem.

Next steps

Based on the activities and observations, future steps will include the development and implementation of standards in (more) sub-disciplines within chemistry, while focusing on MI standards.

The true value of publishing comes when it is actively being reused straight from the repositories and new hypotheses and knowledge are derived.